

METHODS AND TECHNOLOGIES OF DEVELOPMENT OF EMOTIONAL STABILITY IN PRESCHOOL CHILDREN WITH THE HELP OF PHYSICAL CULTURE

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Abstract. *Improving the system of protecting and strengthening children's health, forming a culture of health and motivation for a healthy lifestyle in them should become one of the priorities of the activities of the preschool educational organization. The article talks about physical education of preschool children.*

Keywords: *physical education of preschool children, health, healthy child, physical development.*

Action games are an important complex educational process. Children's movement activity, which is the basis of this process, has a positive effect on physical development, the formation of movement skills and physical qualities, and strengthening of health by increasing the functional activity of the body and enhancing feelings of emotional joy. Action games, as one of the main means and methods of physical education, help to effectively solve the tasks listed above.

Educational methods consist of various combinations of the system of methods depending on the specific characteristics of the educational subject, specific didactic tasks, tools and educational conditions. The nervous system and the whole body of a preschool child are extremely plastic and susceptible to external influences. Therefore, the right ratio of mental and physical effort and the final rest should be one of the important tasks of the educator when training with children of preschool age.

The following methods are used in the education of children of preschool age, taking into account their age characteristics and capabilities.

1. Demonstration method.
2. Oral method.
3. Practical method.
4. Game method.
5. Competition method.

The visual method ensures the brightness of emotional perception and movement sensations. They are necessary for the formation of a very complete and clear image of the movement that activates the development of sensory abilities in children. Verbal method is a method aimed at children's minds, it helps them to understand the tasks set before them and consciously perform movement exercises that play a big role in mastering the content and structure of the exercises, it helps to use these exercises independently in different situations. The practical method is related to children's practical movement activities and ensures that the movements are correctly perceived in their motor senses. Practical methods are characterized by the use of exercises in the form of games, competition elements. One of the different types of practical method is the game method. The game method is effective in working with children and takes into

account the elements of visual image and visual practical thinking. It allows simultaneous improvement of various movement skills, independence of movements, quick response to changing conditions, and creative activity.

The competition method can be used only in the conditions of pedagogical leadership in teaching children of preschool age. This method can be used in large groups. It is a mandatory condition of the competition that the competitions should be suitable for children's strength, education of moral and willful qualities, as well as correct assessment of one's own achievements and the successes of other children based on a conscious attitude to the audience. The importance of the competition method is very great in training voluntary and moral qualities such as initiative, determination, perseverance, courage, bravery, nobility, friendship. However, it should not be forgotten that competing and fighting for the first place can allow negative traits (selfishness, jealousy, rudeness, etc.) to develop. Therefore, the competition method can justify its role in the field of spiritual education only if it is skillfully guided by the pedagogy. Educational methods are used in the pedagogical process. Immediately after visual or verbal methods, children should move on to practical activities, independent performance of activities. Each method consists of a set of several methods that help solve tasks. The method is a part of the method, its complement and clarifying part. Methods related to the demonstration method - various methods of demonstration are used to teach children to perform actions. Visualization methods are the correct and clear demonstration of movement or certain elements of movement by the educator; from imitating the views of life around; use of targeting in the correct passage of the module; consists of the use of demonstration manuals, television broadcasts, photographs, pictures.

Tactile muscle-visibility is ensured by the inclusion of physical education manuals in children's movement activities. For example: in order to develop the skill of running with a high knee, arc-shaped gates placed in a row are used. Lifting the leg over these obstacles while running helps the child to master the skill of raising the knee high.

Audible methods are based on the control of movements by sound. Instrumental music and singing are the best auditory exhibits. They arouse aesthetic feeling and emotional excitement in children, determine the character of movement, control its pace and rhythm. Teachers also use tambourines to control the pace and rhythm of movement. Demonstration methods help the child to correctly perceive and imagine actions, to expand his emotional consciousness, to develop self-control in performing actions, to control the pace and rhythm through hearing, and to develop sensory abilities.

Methods of oral method-verbal methods of teaching actions are expressed in the following:

Explaining to children what they have in their lives based on experience and imagination, new actions are clear, in a short time is explained.

The interpretation method is an interpretation based on clearly showing actions or identifying some of its elements.

The method of giving instructions is the instructions that are necessary when repeating the actions shown by the teacher or when the children perform the exercises independently.

The interview method is pre-interviews when it is required to introduce new physical exercises and movement games and to explain them when teaching movements, to clarify the plot of the movement game.

The method of asking questions, the educator asks children questions in order to determine the level of understanding of the consistency of actions before performing physical exercises, or to check whether there is an idea about meaningful action games, to clarify the rules, game actions. Method of ordering and giving signals. For example, "Stop! Run one, two, three", "Jump and spread your legs shoulder width apart!" These commands require different intonations and dynamics that make the children's response speed and accuracy. These include counting aloud and expressively pronouncing the beginnings of the game.

Expressive meaningful narrative method. It is used in order to develop expressiveness in actions and better access to the image of the game. A meaningful story is like telling a short story (1.5-2 minutes). In this case, the educator reveals the content and rules of the game in a short pictorial story. For example: "When there is no, there is a white mother goat with a beautiful gray horn and plain gray. As long as she has children..." "The purposeful combination of visual and verbal methods in teaching children, their interdependence, the accuracy and imagery of the perception and repetition of actions, and the action tasks performed by children, they provide a conscious understanding of the content and consistency of all elements of each movement activity.

Methods related to the practical method When teaching children to move, the educator uses a variety of practical methods interrelated with visual and verbal methods. He performs exercises, some roles in action games, the role of manager, involves children in tasks and encourages them to participate in competitions by setting an example. For example, who performs a movement task faster, better, more correctly, he shows children how to behave and how to behave. plans accordingly. All methods and methods should be used in combination with each other when teaching physical activities to children. In the process of physical education, children acquire movement skills and abilities.

Movement skill is determined by the level of mastery of movement technique. Two types of movement skills are distinguished: one of them is performed as a whole movement activity, and the other is expressed in individual movements of different complexity. The first type of skills is related to games and fights. The development of the second type of movement skills goes from the initial mastery of the movement technique to its improvement.

Movement skill is the level of mastery of movement technique.

In it, the control of movements takes place automatically, and the movements are their own is distinguished by its stability. The formation of movement skills consists of the process of the emergence of a dynamic stereotype in the interaction of the first and second signal systems. Movement skills are of great practical importance for a child. The acquired skills allow to use physical and mental forces efficiently, to quickly and accurately perform actions that are part of integrated movement activity.

The healing effect achieved by active games is inextricably linked with the positive emotions that arise during children's play and have a positive effect on the child's psyche. Emotional excitement awakens in children the desire to achieve a goal common to all, and it is expressed in a clear understanding of tasks, mutual compatibility of actions, accurate targeting in space and game conditions, and accelerated execution of tasks. Due to children's strong desire to achieve the goal and enjoyable pursuit, the role of will, which helps to overcome various obstacles, increases.

Movement games serve as a method of improving movement skills acquired by children and training physical qualities. During the game, the child focuses on achieving the goal, not on

the method of performing the action. He acts according to the conditions of the game, showing agility and thus improving the movements. That is why, for example, the game "Wolf in the gorge" is given after the children learn to run and jump.

As a movement activity, movement play has certain special features: it requires the child to quickly respond to signals and sudden changes in the game. Different situations and actions that occur in the game require changes in the level of muscle tension. For example, in the "Trap" game, each child must carefully follow the leader's actions: when the leader approaches him, he quickly runs away in the opposite direction; when he feels safe, he moves slowly and stops; accelerates again when the starter approaches.

Almost every action game has actions and cues for children's movements. Such active movement activities train the child's nervous system, improving and balancing the processes of excitation and inhibition, as well as observation, resourcefulness, the ability to aim in a changing environment, find a way out of a difficult situation, quickly educates decision-making and its implementation, bravery, initiative, choosing an independent way to achieve the goal.

The origin of action games goes back to ancient folk pedagogy. Children of early age are brought up in families with the help of toys and fun games related to the child's initial movements. In the life of children older than that, folk games with colorful action content (including game beginnings that frame children, khyrgyi, counting) have a great place. All of these still retain their artistic appeal, educational value and constitute valuable game folklore.

The game is the main type of activity in the all-round development of children. The more a child plays at a young age, the better it will be at school and later on at work. The game is a bright type of the child's activity, during the game his will, feelings, needs, interests, impressionability, that is, his whole personality is formed.

A game is a process aimed at acting and understanding social reality. If there are interesting actions performed with basic objects for young children, as the child grows up, it serves to reflect the actions and relationships of adults in the game. Since ancient times, children of the Uzbek people have been taught by playing various folk games, and through games, qualities such as perseverance, agility, resourcefulness, and kindness are formed and taught to work.

The selection and planning of active and fewer active games is carried out according to the program. It takes into account the conditions of each age group, such as the general level of physical and mental development of children, the development of motor skills, the state of health of each child, individual typological characteristics, season, daily routine, play the location of the transfer, as well as the specific characteristics of children's interests.

The conditional real situation of plot role-playing games helps the child to recreate a familiar life image. The child enjoys the actions themselves, imitating birds and animals: he flies like a bird, jumps like a rabbit, runs like a mare. That's why laughter and happy shouts are heard during the game, and the basis of the game process is the child's simple performance activity, the first attempts to enter the image of the game.

National games develop children's strength and abilities, prepare them for life. National action games, like other genres of folklore, have reached us over a long history. Through the national games, the child's speech grows, mental abilities develop, and it is ensured that he grows physically agile and strong. The Uzbek national games help to raise children as believers, believers, intellectually mature and healthy.

Sports games - these include volleyball, basketball, badminton, football, lapta, table tennis, football, hockey.

In sports games, first of all, the age characteristics of children of preschool age are taken into account, therefore, only simple rules of movement technique, real elements of game organization are selected. Due to this, game factors do not cause physical and nervous tension as in adults. At the same time, they cultivate a sense of purpose, camaraderie, responsibility, and love for sports.

They have elements of children's competition, game relay. Sports games are gradually introduced when they play organized movement games and independently organize movement games. Sports games require more self-control, organization, observation, certain movement techniques, quick reaction of movement than in action games. If children show creative initiative in active games and use different actions, in sports games, the actions are somewhat limited, which is determined by the specific characteristics of this game and the accuracy of the movement activity technique.

The number of participants in sports games is clearly defined, their tasks are divided, and the duration of the game is limited. The conditions for holding games require a specially prepared place, a designated field, appropriate equipment and inventory.

It is desirable to change the simple action games. However, it is possible to diversify the game not only to maintain children's interest in it, but also to improve the actions of pedagogical tasks, to perform somewhat complex game actions, to train the physical qualities necessary for the change of the conditions of the game situation. is necessary. They require children to have a certain mental and physical strength and, at the same time, a growing interest in the game.

In the planning of physical training activities, the main activities of children and youth are based on the normative documents "State Requirements for Preschool Education" and the Improved "Bolajon" base program for preschool educational institutions: walking, running, jumping, it is indicated that it is necessary to know and play the names of national, moving and peaceful games such as jumping-crawling, jumping over obstacles. It is more difficult for the physical education instructor to divide the basic movements such as walking, running, jumping, throwing, climbing, balance exercises into 85 exercises in a consistent manner. During their planning, it is necessary not only to take into account the training conditions (room, equipment, etc.), the children's readiness, but also to pay attention to the consistent formation of each movement skill.

This is achieved by choosing more exercises and games of increasing complexity. It is of great importance to plan to combine the main actions with each other more appropriately during the training, as well as to use organizational methods that ensure a high level of activity of children. Repetition of material also plays an important role. It is better to repeat the same movement every 3-4 weeks. It is advisable to include several (two to four) consistently performed exercises for each type of movement to be studied. Usually, exercises are chosen for training, which are related to different stages of children's education: one of the tasks is often related to learning new exercises or repeating parts of the movement, while others are related to strengthening skills and will be aimed at improvement.

In the preschool educational organization, physical education classes are divided into 86 days of the week depending on the child's physiological condition 2 times a week in all groups. In pre-school educational institutions, the physical education instructor shapes the activities based on

the age characteristics of the children. In the system of physical education in a preschool educational institution - routine, traditional activities, embodied activities, exercise (natural and artificial), physical exercises, cultural hygiene skills, morning and evening hours, happy moments, therapeutic gymnastics, rhythmic, sports games are organized.

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